

MATILDE

SOCIAL MEDIA ONLINE TOOLS AND WEBSITE CATALOGUE

Deliverable 7.3

MATILDE

MATILDE has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 870831

Call: H2020-SC6-MIGRATION-2019

Work Programmes:

H2020-EU.3.6.1.1. The mechanisms to promote smart, sustainable and inclusive growth

H2020-EU.3.6.1.2. Trusted organisations, practices, services and policies that are necessary to build resilient, inclusive, participatory, open and creative societies in Europe, in particular taking into account migration, integration and demographic change

Deliverable 7.3 Social Media Online Tools and Website

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Summary

This document is a deliverable of the MATILDE project, funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 870831.

MATILDE aims to examine how migration impacts local development and territorial cohesion, with a specific focus on European rural and mountain regions. As part of the Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) of the project, social media and website developed and executed by STL (Support to Life). This catalogue aims to present the communication and dissemination tools created.

1. Website

MATILDE website has developed by STL in subtask 7.3.1 in the beginning of the project and used throughout the project actively.

Figure 1. Main page of the website

Figure 2. Display of the map on the mainpage

1.1. About

First section of the project website includes the description of the project, project partners, supporting partners, twin projects and advisory boards.

Figure 3. Project partners

Figure 4. Twin projects

Figure 5. About MATILDE

1.2. Concepts

Concepts section of the project website displays the concept and methods that will guide, work packages and their contents, objective and expected results from MATILDE.

Figure 6. Work packages

Figure 7. Objective and expected results

Figure 8. Concepts & Methods Page

1.3. Results

Website has been updated regularly; outputs of the project have been displayed in the Reports & Policy Briefs section. Additionally, Scientific & Policy Results section was created in order to display the outputs and achievements of the project in the timeline.

During the project, local partner translations' of the project outputs (reports and policy briefs) have been gathered in a special section entitled Reports in Local Languages.

Figure 9. Reports section

Figure 10. Local language translations of the reports

Figure 11. Scientific & Policy Results timeline

In the second project period, Self-Assessment Toolbox for Practitioners & Policy Makers and International MATILDE Conference was uploaded to the 'Results' section of the website.

Figure 12. MATILDE Toolbox

Figure 13. International MATILDE Conference

1.4. Citizen & Media

Project website, as an open platform for partners and stakeholders, has been actively used throughout the project. Blog posts by partners about action research, [newsletters](#) and [press releases](#) were disseminated regularly.

[Blog section](#) of the MATILDE website was created to be an open platform for partners and stakeholders of the project. Communicable deliverables have been produced by research partners, blog articles have been composed by associated experts, Citizen engagement activities and field research outputs of the partners have been the main sources of the blog section.

Figure 14 Press Releases

Figure 15. Newsletters

matilde-migration.eu

Figure 16. Blog Post Section

During the MATILDE project span, tasks such as MATILDE [postcards](#), [photo contest](#), [essay contest](#) have been designed to stimulate reflection and elaboration on the impact of migration and to promote awareness about the project's results. These activities are important to create a critical reflection about the perception related to migration.

Figure 17. Postcards

Figure 18. Essay Contest

Figure 19. Photo Contest

In order to target a diversified, non-specialist audience, also a [virtual gallery](#) was created. This gallery is a multimedia space which displays the content collected during the case studies, such as photos, informative texts and videos.

[Local media coverages](#) section has been dedicated to media appearances of the project in local languages.

Figure 20. Press Coverage Section

Figure 21. Virtual Gallery

1.5. Learning

Migration Facts and MATILDE regions have been created in the beginning of the MATILDE project. Regions sections provide an overview information on 13 MATILDE regions with their location on the map.

Figure 22 MATILDE Regions

The MOOC (Massive Online Open Courses) is designed for anyone interested in regional development, rural and mountain areas as well as international (and even internal) migration. Students are expected to read the required texts before class, follow the PPT Slides, and listen to the videos depicting the content of respective lecture. MOOC is open for everyone who registers.

The Impact Of International Migration On Remote Places

MOOC on "Evaluating and enhancing the impact of international migration on rural and mountain areas" will offer a far-reaching training on the conceptual, methodological and policy-oriented results of MATILDE.

10 Lessons Total 19 hours 58 minutes

START THE COURSE

Figure 23. MOOC main page

A special page was created for MATILDE Summer School, focusing on methodologies and tools to investigate the impact of international migration in rural and mountain areas. Summer school was held on 13-17 June 2022 in Bussoleno Valley, Italy; 25 young researchers and practitioners from EU and non-EU countries participated.

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SUMMER SCHOOL

The Summer School Committee has selected the participants and submission period is over. Thank you for your interest.

CALL FOR APPLICATIONS

MATILDE Summer School

International Migration in Remote Places

Bussoleno, Susa Valley, Italy

Organised by: MATILDE Research Partners led by the University of Eastern Finland

Date: June 13-17, 2022

Submissions Deadline: April 15, 2022 (GMT)

Venue: Polo Logistico Protezione Civile "Valle di Susa" – Croce Rossa Italiana Via Cascina del Gallo, 5, 10053 Bussoleno, (Turin), Italy

MATILDE a 3-year project funded by EU Horizon 2020 facility, focuses on the impact of migration on the local development of remote places of Europe. The Summer School, organised by the project, aims to provide participants with interdisciplinary knowledge on the social and economic impacts of migration, with a special focus on their interactions with territorial inequalities, sustainable development, and spatial justice. It conveys evidence and results that point to the need to think locally and avoid generalisations in elaborating new approaches to the governance of migration and migrant inclusion.

The summer school seeks to strengthen the link between research, teaching and learning, and guide the participants to develop their argumentation and critical analytical thinking. This is expected to allow the participants to enhance their reflective learning outcomes as they will not only benefit directly from the most up-to-date research, but also have an opportunity to bring a contribution to it and take part in the co-production of knowledge.

CALL FOR APPLICATIONS

MATILDE Summer School

SUBMISSION DEADLINE 15 APRIL 2022

13-17 June 2022
Bussoleno, Susa Valley, Italy

Figure 24. Summer School Main Page

1.6. Contact

info@matilde-migration.eu e-mail address was used throughout the project.

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CONTACT

For queries, suggestions or interview requests, you may write to us via info@matilde-migration.eu

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Figure 25. Contact section

2.Social Media

MATILDE has Twitter, Facebook, Instagram and LinkedIn accounts. While the former three are gaining visibility with the general public, the latter one is best suited to engage professional communities and specialized stakeholders. In the second period of the project, a Youtube channel was created for visual outputs of the project.

Every MATILDE project partner was expected to contribute to MATILDE’s social media activity with at least 6 social media posts throughout the project, and with at least 6 reports of the social media posts shared by MATILDE accounts, with a brief introductory note. All partners, when engaging in project-related communication through their institutional accounts, were expected to use the hashtag #MATILDEmigration.

2.1. Twitter

As of M35, twitter account of MATILDE (@MATILDE_Mig) has 585 followers.

Figure 26. MATILDE Twitter profile

Figure 27. MATILDE Twitter Analytics Page

2.2. Facebook

Facebook page of the MATILDE project (@MatildeProject) has 497 likes and 560 followers, as of M35.

Figure 28. MATILDE Facebook profile

2.3. Instagram

As of M35, Instagram page of the project (@matildemigration) has 287 followers.

Figure 29. MATILDE Instagram profile

2.4. LinkedIn

LinkedIn page of the MATILDE project ([MATILDE Migration](#)) has 147 likes, as of M35.

Figure 30. MATILDE LinkedIn profile

2.5. Youtube

As of M35, Youtube page of the project ([@matildemigration4701](#)) has 13 followers.

Figure 31. MATILDE Youtube Profile